

HOW TO IMPROVE INTERESTS OF BEGINNER STUDENTS IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

This article is about how to improve students' curiosity during teaching English. Moreover, this article shows the best way to enhance interests of beginner students. Actually, these ways help to learn the lessons effectively. Not only methods must be easy, but also methods must entail.

Introduction

It is known that a lot of students acquire much knowledge through interest. If beginner students are quick at understanding new concepts when presented in a positive engaging way, level of students' understanding improve. Teacher need to choose right suitable student's age. To be more precise, the teacher should use a method that simplifies it for learners. And this method must appeal to young and old learners alike. Learner's curiosity will often help to understand. "The teaching of foreign language and international understanding to children can be extremely fulfilling due to the responsiveness of the audience. When planning activities, try to look out for things that the children are interested in something. Use these examples to capture the students' attention and interest, for example: creating a syllabus; the group game; bodybuilding game, criss-cross game, and other games [1]. It helps to improve beginner students in teaching.

How to improve interests of beginner students in teaching English? – Each person answer differently, this is because each person has different thinking and acquiring. A lot of

researches have shown that using attractive games, methods in EFL classrooms is one of the efficient structures in teaching English. Method of the teacher should be creative, independence and higher order thinking. Usually, some children have aspired to the leadership of own profession, but often they require to help. There are many ways with the help of which teacher can improve the topic to beginner learners. Many students ascribe their success to their teacher's constant encouragement and support. This is because some students want to sustain their interest not only their own, but also their teachers. "Teaching beginners can be a daunting prospect.

1) Keep instructions clear and simple – it can be tempting when addressing a class of students, ones that you've only just met, to explain activities in your politest language;

2) Let them listen first – don't pressure students into speaking before they've had lots of opportunity to listen to you using it;

3) Drill, repeat, drill, repeat, drill... – It might seem boring to go over the same sentences again and again, but it is necessary;

4) Establish classroom language early on – It's much better to equip students early on with classroom language that will help them navigate the lesson smoothly;

5) Avoid metalanguage – There's no point in students knowing the terms past simple, irregular verb or adverb of frequency if they can't use the actual structures or words they refer to;

6) Don't forget that your students are fluent in their own language(s) – the most important is pronunciation;

7) Prepare well, prepare a lot, keep them talking – Ensure you have a range of activities to use, and don't go into class without having first carefully thought through how you are going to introduce new language" [1].

"Here are seven ways to start teaching English to beginners, step by step:

1. Break up lessons and categorize vocabulary – Think about how hard it is to learn a foreign language. It can be overwhelming at first. Learning English is no easy task. ESL students need structure. Try creating lesson plans with small activities broken down into manageable chunks to help them absorb remember everything;

2. Repeat everything – Don't be afraid to be a broken record. Getting in the habit of repeating things will help your beginner students understand the lesson and key phrases and words better. If you begin every class with a greeting like, "Hello, how are you?" students will quickly get comfortable with replying to and using this greeting;

3. Use plenty of props – Imagine how you might describe what a cat is to someone who doesn't speak English. The reality is you can say whatever you like, but the simplest thing would be to show them a picture of a cat or draw a cat on the board;

4. Embrace your inner mime – There will also be times where you need to explain what a cat is, but you don't have a picture to

reference or space on the board to draw one. So, what's the next most straightforward thing you can do? Let out a couple of meows and act it out;

5. Check for understanding – Even after you've given great instructions, shown a picture, and done an Oscar-worthy mime, you'll still sometimes end up with a class of clueless faces looking back at you. When teaching Basic English to beginners, it can be hard to gauge how much students understand. And often, through no fault of their own, they may completely misunderstand what you're asking them;

6. Get into group activities – Sometimes it can be hard to get students in beginner classes to form a bond, especially if they are all from different countries and don't share a common language. Singing songs and chants is a great way to build group activities into a beginner class while improving fluency and focusing on repetition;

7. Give plenty of encouragement – For learners at this level, everything is new and they are bound to make mistake when they speak and write in English. They know this as much as you do and might need more praise and encouragement to keep going [2].

1) Task-based Approach – represents a significant paradigm shift since the focus on content has shifted to skills and competencies. So, planning and design aren't about what's taught, but why it's taught;

2) Project-based Approach – is meant to address students' real needs by adapting language to the skills and competencies they truly need personally and/or professionally;

3) Lexical Syllabus – this approach is based upon the core language that students need to know given their needs. Again, professional students need very specific vocabulary pertaining to their field. For instance, "profit" is an essential term for

business students; much the same way “scalpel” is to medical students;

4) Using Smart phones in the Classroom such as dictionary, translator and grammar reference apps. Much like computers, students need to understand that their phones aren’t for play or personal use, but to be used as learning tools”. [3] There are a lot of techniques for improving students’ oral skills in English: “Oral language is one of the most important skills your students can master – both for social and academic success. Learners use this skill throughout the day to process and deliver instructions, make requests, ask questions, receive new information, and interact with peers, such as encourage conversation, modal syntactic structure, maintain eye contact,

remind students to speak loudly, explain the subtleties of tone” [4], and other methods can help for speaking.

Conclusion

Research shows that there are a lot of types, methods of improving learners in teaching. Every person want to choose and suitable own capability. And even there are so many games that can be used in teaching English, we’ll be able to select. Teachers can exploit any number of approaches: utilize of games, songs, competitions, and attractive methods. The curiosity is a key of the success learning of students to improve in teaching English. Experienced teacher can attract children to lesson.

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